

The wellbeing of PhD-students in Germany

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Purpose

Health makes a significant contribution to the success or failure of educational and career paths and thus functions as an important resource. The German Social Survey (Middendorff et al., 2017, p. 36) shows that around one in ten students has health impairments that impede their studies. Despite this obvious relevance, research in Germany has rarely addressed the issue of health. This applies even more to the academic qualification phase of the doctorate, because comparable figures for doctoral students have not even been available up to now.

Internationally, scientific qualification phases and potential health burdens associated with them have already been reported more frequently in the media and research (e.g., Gewin, 2012; Nature, 2019). Current literature suggests that across different occupational groups (Levecque et al., 2017, Casey et al., 2022) academics are among those with the highest levels of common mental disorders (alongside social services staff and teachers). Leveque has found that doctoral students suffer more often from depressive symptoms, sleep problems, or feelings of permanent stress compared to a non-promoting comparison group (Levecque et al., 2017). Studies also provide indications of which aspects of working conditions in science may be responsible for health impairments. These include, for example, conflicts between work and family life and a high workload (Levecque et al., 2017), as well as the difficulty of finding permanent employment (Reevy & Deason, 2014). But up to now, data and research in Germany has been scarce.

Design

With the National Academics Panel Study (Nacaps), a broad database on PhD-students is available for Germany for the first time. Nacaps is a representative, longitudinal survey with several cohorts. It collects data on the general situation and career progression of doctoral candidates and doctorate holders in Germany. This is the first effort in Germany to systematically collect data on career paths of highly qualified academics. In all cohorts and all waves, Nacaps also addresses the topic of (mental) health. The four core questions of the CDC-HRQOL-4 (Moriarty et al., 2003) are used to measure health-related quality of life. This construct, which is closely linked to the concept of well-being, is based on a subjective and multidimensional definition of health that includes physical, psychological and social aspects. It is available in English, Spanish, and German and has been used in numerous international studies (e.g., Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System, China Chronic Disease and Risk Factor Surveillance, National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, Medicare Health Outcomes Survey), allowing cross-cultural comparisons. Therefore, the Nacaps data allow to study the development of mental well-being throughout the doctoral phase, its causes, and its consequences – and also in comparison to other groups in Germany.

Results

First analyses of the Nacaps data already reveal findings that point to options for action for universities, supervisors, and policymakers. People who report good support during the doctoral phase also report fewer health restrictions more frequently. Similarly, good health is associated with thoughts of dropping out: the better off the doctoral researchers are, the less often they think about quitting. In addition, individuals with higher disposable income during the doctoral phase more often report that they are also in good health. Interestingly, however, no correlation was found between the duration of the employment contract and health.

Implications

This new data set provides new insights and opportunities for research. And already the first analyses point to opportunities for action that can be taken by universities and policymakers. In addition, the comparability of the health questions with other international studies also provides the opportunity for international research.

Resources

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